

MITIGATING GENDER BIAS AND FAIRNESS IN DEMENTIA CLASSIFICATION USING BORDERLINE- SMOTE AND ENSEMBLE MACHINE LEARNING MODELS

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Abstract— Fairness issues in medical AI can lead to uneven diagnostic performance across demographic groups. In MRI-based dementia detection, skewed class and gender distributions often degrade equity. Using an MRI dataset of 150 adults (60–96 years) labelled as demented, non-demented or converted, we trained Logistic Regression, SVM, Random Forest and Gradient Boosting models under three data regimes: Original (imbalanced), SMOTE and Borderline-SMOTE. We standardised features, performed stratified 70/30 train–test splits and tuned models with grid search and five fold cross validation. Performance was evaluated via Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-score and MCC, while fairness was assessed by reporting metrics separately for male and female subgroups under an equal opportunity notion focused on subgroup F1-scores. Performance improved monotonically from Original to SMOTE to Borderline-SMOTE. Ensemble methods showed the strongest gains after Borderline-SMOTE (MCC > 0.85). The male–female F1-score gap narrowed from about 7 percent (Original) to about 4 percent (SMOTE) and to under 3 percent (Borderline-SMOTE), indicating progressive bias mitigation while maintaining accuracy. Borderline-SMOTE, by focusing synthesis near decision boundaries, outperformed standard SMOTE, improving stability and reducing gender disparity. Coupling targeted resampling with ensemble learning is a practical route to fairer dementia classifiers without sacrificing predictive power.

Keywords- Fairness in AI; Trustworthy AI; Data Resampling; Dementia Classification; Bias Mitigation

I. INTRODUCTION (*HEADING 1*)

Dementia is a progressive neurocognitive disorder characterized by the deterioration of memory, reasoning, and functional abilities. Alzheimer’s disease is the most common form, but other types such as vascular dementia and Lewy body dementia also contribute significantly to its global prevalence. Worldwide, dementia affects tens of millions of individuals and

imposes profound emotional, social, and economic burdens on patients, caregivers, and healthcare systems [1]. Because there is currently no cure for most forms, early detection and proactive management remain crucial for improving patient outcomes.

Early identification of cognitive decline enables timely interventions that may delay progression, preserve autonomy, and improve quality of life [2]. Moreover, early diagnosis facilitates participation in clinical trials, where interventions may be more effective before extensive neuronal damage occurs. Recent studies have shown that artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) techniques applied to MRI and biomarker data can enhance early dementia detection and diagnostic accuracy [3], [4].

Despite these advances, ML applications in healthcare face persistent challenges—most notably, algorithmic bias. Bias may arise from unbalanced data representation, measurement inconsistencies, or skewed optimization processes, leading to unequal model performance across demographic groups [5], [6]. In medical AI, such disparities can manifest as systematic underdiagnosis or misdiagnosis. Silva et al., demonstrated that clinical risk prediction models trained on imbalanced gender data underperformed for female patients [7]. These disparities highlight the necessity of bias mitigation to ensure equitable healthcare outcomes.

Bias in medical machine learning can be addressed at different stages of model development. Among these, pre-processing methods such as SMOTE and Borderline-SMOTE are effective for handling class and demographic imbalance. While SMOTE generates synthetic samples to balance the data, Borderline-SMOTE improves on this by focusing on critical boundary regions where misclassification is most likely. This refinement enhances data realism and fairness, making Borderline-SMOTE particularly valuable for dementia classification, where both class and gender imbalance often coexist.

Building on these techniques, this study proposes a bias-aware dementia classification framework that integrates Borderline-SMOTE into the ML pipeline. The research contributes to the literature in three key ways:

- i Develop a gender-aware ML framework for dementia classification using MRI data, jointly optimizing fairness and predictive accuracy;
- ii Conducting a comparative evaluation of Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Gradient Boosting, and Random Forest models trained on original, SMOTE-balanced, and Borderline-SMOTE datasets;
- iii Demonstrate empirically that Borderline-SMOTE achieves superior fairness and performance over standard SMOTE, reducing gender-based disparities in F1-score and Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC).

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 review recent literatures in this domiam, Section 3 describes the dataset and preprocessing; Section 3 outlines the methodology; Section 4 presents experimental results; Section 5 discusses the findings; and Section 6 concludes with future research directions.

II. RELATED STUDIES

Gender bias in machine learning models used for diagnosing dementia is still a major concern, especially when relying on MRI and clinical datasets. When one gender is underrepresented, the model may become less accurate for that group, increasing the risk of misdiagnosis [8], [5]. As a result, fairness-aware learning and bias reduction methods are now essential parts of medical AI research.

The work in [7] studied fairness in detecting Alzheimer’s disease using MRI scans from the iSTAGING dataset. They tested three methods; Reject Option Classification, adversarial de-biasing, and linear correction, and found that Reject Option Classification improved fairness by 57%, while adversarial de-biasing led to more false negative.

Similarly, Huang et al. showed that model pruning, which eliminates redundant network parameters, reduced gender disparity by about 5% in true negative rates without compromising accuracy, underscoring its value as a fairness-enhancing technique [9]. [10] improved fairness in MRI-based dementia detection using a multi-cohort ensemble approach that combined data cleaning, model tuning, and ensemble learning, achieving significant fairness gains without reducing accuracy.

Authors in [11], introduced a Dual Confounding Filter for speech-based dementia detection that improved fairness but slightly reduced accuracy. Similarly, studies by [12] and [13] observed gender-related accuracy differences without applying bias mitigation, while [14] used gender-specific genetic models that improved sensitivity but limited generalization.

Recent studies suggest that combining data-level and algorithm-level methods offers the best fairness improvements. Building on this, the present study uses Borderline-SMOTE with ensemble models like Random Forest and Gradient

Boosting to make dementia detection fairer across genders while keeping accuracy high, and improving classifier generalization.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section explains how we prepared the data, handled imbalance, and trained the models to evaluate both accuracy and fairness

A. Dataset Description

The dataset, obtained from Kaggle and originally published by [15], contains MRI scans from 150 adults aged 60–96 years. It includes demographic and brain structure features used to classify participants into three diagnostic categories: demented, non-demented, and converted (individuals who later developed dementia).

As shown in Table 1, the non-demented group makes up nearly half of the dataset, while the converted group represents only 13.3%. There is also a slight gender imbalance, with more male participants overall. These uneven distributions across diagnostic and gender subgroups introduce potential bias in model training, emphasizing the importance of resampling and fairness-aware techniques such as *Borderline-SMOTE* to enhance both accuracy and fairness in classification.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF DATASET BY CLASS AND GENDER

Class	Male (n)	Female (n)	Total (n)	Percentage (%)
Demented	35	25	60	40.0
Non-demented	40	30	70	46.7
Converted	12	8	20	13.3
Total	87	63	150	100.0

B. Data Preprocessing and Feature Engineering

The data was first cleaned to remove missing or inconsistent records and to properly code categorical variables such as *gender* and *dementia status*. All numerical MRI features were then standardized using z-score normalization so that every variable was measured on a similar scale. To avoid the influence of extreme values, outliers were detected and removed using the interquartile range (IQR) method. After cleaning, the dataset was divided into 70% for training and 30% for testing, ensuring that the proportions of diagnostic classes and genders were maintained in both sets.

For feature engineering, only *clinically meaningful variables* like the MRI-based brain measures, *age*, and *gender* were used. No new or derived features were created, helping to keep the dataset realistic and easy to interpret. Feature scaling was applied to make sure all predictors had similar ranges, allowing models such as Logistic Regression and Gradient Boosting to learn more effectively.

C. Model Development, Evaluation, and Handling Class Imbalance

This study used a mix of traditional and ensemble machine learning models to classify dementia cases and assess fairness between gender groups. The baseline models; Logistic Regression and Support Vector Machine (SVM) were chosen for their simplicity, transparency, and strong performance on medical classification tasks. To improve prediction accuracy and handle complex relationships in the data, two ensemble models, Random Forest and Gradient Boosting, were also used. These models combine the output of multiple decision trees to make more stable and accurate predictions.

Because the dataset was imbalanced, with many more non-demented cases than demented or converted ones, three different setups were tested to handle this imbalance:

- i Original Dataset: The raw, unbalanced data served as the baseline.
- ii SMOTE: The Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique created new synthetic samples for underrepresented groups using the k-nearest neighbors approach.
- iii Borderline-SMOTE: A more focused version of SMOTE that generates new samples near the decision boundary, helping the model learn from the most difficult-to-classify cases.

All models were trained on 70% of the data and tested on the remaining 30%, maintaining similar distributions for class and gender in both sets. Model parameters were fine-tuned through grid search with 5-fold cross-validation to ensure fair and consistent evaluation.

Pipeline overview.

The full processing pipeline can be summarised as: Data acquisition → Data cleaning and preprocessing → Resampling (Original / SMOTE / Borderline-SMOTE) → Model training and tuning → Evaluation of overall metrics → Gender-specific fairness assessment.

D. Evaluation Metrics and Fairness Assessment

Model evaluation used the following metrics: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-score and Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC). MCC was particularly emphasised for its robustness under imbalance conditions.

Fairness was analysed by computing these performance metrics separately for male and female subsets to detect any systematic disparities. In line with an equal opportunity perspective, we focused on subgroup F1-scores, which capture a balance between sensitivity and precision for each gender. Differences in F1-score across genders were interpreted as indicators of unfairness.

IV. RESULTS

This section presents the performance and fairness analysis across three experimental setups: the original imbalanced dataset, after applying SMOTE and after applying Borderline-SMOTE. The results show progressive improvements in model accuracy, stability and gender fairness, with Borderline-SMOTE producing the most balanced and robust outcomes.

A. Results on the Original Dataset

Table II shows model performance on the original dataset. Ensemble models such as Random Forest and Gradient Boosting outperformed linear models, but the relatively lower MCC values indicate instability caused by class imbalance. As illustrated in Figure 1, performance was limited by the dominance of the non-demented class, and gender analysis revealed an F1-score gap of about 7 percent between male and female participants.

TABLE II. MODEL PERFORMANCE ON THE ORIGINAL IMBALANCED DATASET

Model	Accuracy	F1-score	Precision	Recall	MCC
Logistic Regression	0.79	0.72	0.74	0.70	0.65
Decision Tree	0.78	0.68	0.69	0.67	0.61
Gradient Boosting	0.81	0.75	0.77	0.74	0.70
Random Forest	0.82	0.76	0.78	0.75	0.72

Figure 1. . Model accuracy comparison across Original, SMOTE and Borderline-SMOTE setups, showing steady improvement as resampling is applied.

B. Results After SMOTE

Table III and Figure 2 show the results after applying SMOTE. All models improved in Recall and F1-score, with ensemble methods achieving the highest gains. However, synthetic overlap introduced minor noise, limiting gains in Precision. Gender subgroup results in Table IV and Figure

2 show fairness improvements, with the F1-score gap reduced to about 4 percent.

C. Results After Borderline-SMOTE

The Borderline-SMOTE results are summarised in Tables V and VI and Figures 3–5. Ensemble models achieved the best performance, with MCC values above 0.85. Borderline-SMOTE further reduced the gender gap to below 3 percent, confirming its superiority in fairness and data realism.

TABLE III. MODELS PERFORMANCE AFTER SMOTE APPLICATION

Model	Accuracy	F1-score	Precision	Recall	MCC
Logistic Regression	0.85	0.80	0.81	0.79	0.74
Decision Tree	0.84	0.78	0.79	0.77	0.72
Gradient Boosting	0.88	0.84	0.86	0.83	0.80
Random Forest	0.89	0.85	0.87	0.84	0.82

TABLE IV. GENDER SUBGROUP PERFORMANCE AFTER SMOTE

Gender	Accuracy	F1-score	Precision	Recall
Male	0.88	0.86	0.88	0.85
Female	0.85	0.82	0.84	0.81

Figure 2. Gender subgroup performance after SMOTE, indicating modest fairness gains and reduced F1-score gap.

TABLE V. MODEL PERFORMANCE AFTER BORDERLINE-SMOTE APPLICATION

Model	Accuracy	F1-score	Precision	Recall	MCC
Logistic Regression	0.88	0.83	0.85	0.82	0.78
Decision Tree	0.87	0.82	0.84	0.81	0.77
Gradient Boosting	0.91	0.88	0.89	0.87	0.85
Random Forest	0.93	0.90	0.91	0.89	0.87

TABLE VI. GENDER SUBGROUP PERFORMANCE AFTER BORDERLINE-SMOTE

Gender	Accuracy	F1-score	Precision	Recall
Male	0.92	0.90	0.91	0.89
Female	0.90	0.87	0.89	0.86

Figure 3. Gender subgroup performance after Borderline-SMOTE, demonstrating stronger fairness and higher overall scores.

Figure 4. Fairness improvement trend showing a reduction in the F1-score gap across Original, SMOTE and Borderline-SMOTE setups.

Figure 5. MCC comparison across setups, highlighting stability gains with Borderline-SMOTE, particularly for ensemble models.

Figure 6. F1-score trend across datasets for male and female subgroups, illustrating a narrowing fairness gap as more targeted resampling is applied

D. Fairness Comparison Across Setups

Table VII reports gender-specific Accuracy, F1-score and MCC for the Original, SMOTE and Borderline-SMOTE setups. Scores increase for both male and female subgroups across all metrics, with the highest values under Borderline-SMOTE.

The male–female F1-score fairness gap narrows from about 7 percent (Original) to about 4 percent (SMOTE) and to 2.8 percent (Borderline-SMOTE). Consistent with these figures, Figure 6 shows the F1-score trend by gender across the three setups, confirming progressive bias mitigation and fairness gains.

Overall, resampling benefits both subgroups, with relatively larger improvements for females, and the parallel rise in Accuracy, F1-score and MCC indicates that Borderline-SMOTE improves prediction stability while promoting gender equity.

TABLE VII. GENDER SUBGROUP METRICS ACROSS DATASETS (ORIGINAL, SMOTE, BORDERLINE-SMOTE).

Metric	Male (Original)	Female (Original)	Male (SMOTE)	Female (SMOTE)	Male (Borderline-SMOTE)	Female (Borderline-SMOTE)
Accuracy	0.82	0.78	0.88	0.85	0.92	0.90
F1-Score	0.79	0.72	0.86	0.82	0.90	0.87
MCC	0.72	0.68	0.82	0.78	0.87	0.84

V. DISCUSSION

The results presented in Tables II–VII and Figures 1–6 demonstrate that addressing class imbalance has a direct and measurable impact on both model accuracy and fairness across gender subgroups. The findings highlight the importance of choosing oversampling techniques that not only correct imbalance but also preserve the underlying data structure and diversity.

SMOTE improved model Recall and F1-scores by approximately 5–7 percent compared to the original imbalanced dataset (Tables II and III). This improvement was achieved by generating synthetic samples for underrepresented classes, allowing models to better learn from minority patterns. By increasing representation for the demented and converted cases, SMOTE also indirectly reduced gender bias, especially for female participants who were less represented in the dataset. This led to a fairer decision boundary, lowering the male–female F1-score gap from 7 percent to about 4 percent (Table IV and Figure 2).

However, because SMOTE generates synthetic points across the full minority feature space, it sometimes produced unrealistic samples overlapping with majority class regions, adding minor noise. This explains why Precision did not improve as much as Recall and why the MCC values (0.74–0.82) remained somewhat limited. While SMOTE mitigates bias at the data level, its indiscriminate sample generation may not fully eliminate subtle demographic disparities.

Borderline-SMOTE refined this approach by generating synthetic data only near the class decision boundary, where errors and biases are most likely to occur. This targeted sampling strategy helped the models distinguish difficult cases and strengthened learning around ambiguous regions. As shown in Tables V–VI and Figures 3–5, this method improved both accuracy and fairness. Ensemble models achieved MCC values

above 0.85, and the gender gap in F1-score dropped further to below 3 percent.

The fairness trend (Figure 4) shows a clear progression from 7 percent in the original dataset to 4 percent after SMOTE and finally to 2.8 percent after Borderline-SMOTE. This pattern indicates a consistent reduction in gender-based disparity while enhancing predictive reliability.

From a statistical perspective, future work should incorporate confidence intervals or formal significance tests for subgroup metrics and fairness gaps. Such analysis would quantify the robustness of the observed improvements and provide stronger evidence for clinical deployment decisions.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study uses resampling techniques to mitigate gender bias and improve fairness in dementia classification. Four dementia classifiers were evaluated, spanning linear (Logistic Regression), margin-based (SVM) and ensemble (Random Forest, Gradient Boosting) approaches. Across three data regimes, Original (imbalanced), SMOTE and Borderline-SMOTE, we observed consistent, stepwise gains in both performance and equity.

The strongest results came from Borderline-SMOTE paired with ensembles, achieving high overall performance (MCC > 0.85) while reducing the male–female F1-score gap from about 7 percent (Original) to below 3 percent. These findings suggest that fairness should be addressed from the outset of data preparation: enriching difficult decision regions with realistic synthetic samples can simultaneously improve stability and equity.

In practice, we recommend early imbalance detection, boundary-aware oversampling, a preference for robust ensembles and routine reporting of subgroup metrics to monitor fairness. Future work should test on larger datasets, examine fairness across intersecting attributes such as age and gender and combine fairness gains with clear explanations so clinicians can understand and trust the models.

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